

E-CADHERIN AND KI67 CORRELATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH LYMPH NODE METASTASES FROM GASTRIC CANCER

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of this study is to investigate the correlation of immunohistochemical expression of the epithelial marker E-cadherin and the proliferative marker Ki – 67 in patients with lymph node metastases from gastric carcinoma.

Materials and methods: The study includes a retrospective and prospective study of 158 cases with histologically diagnosed gastric carcinoma for a period of seven years (2013-2020) from the array of the Departments of Clinical Pathology of UMHAT "Kaspela", Plovdiv and UMHAT "Pulmed", Plovdiv. All studied cases were divided into 2 groups : Intestinal type (n=97) and Diffuse type (n=61). 33 cases of patients with gastric carcinoma with lymph node metastases were selected for immunohistochemical study with E-cadherin and Ki 67. The tissue was processed with standard histopathological and immunohistochemical techniques according to standard protocols of the manufacturer using the Bond Polymer Refine Detection imaging system.

Results: In the lymph node metastases group, positive linear membranous or intracytoplasmic granular E-cadherin expression was found in > 10% of tumor cells in all lymph node metastases studied, but with significant variations in intensity and percentage of positive cells between individual cases. Both in the general group and in the groups of lymph node metastases of intestinal and diffuse type of GC, the proportion of cases with reduced E-cadherin expression/positive EMT status was predominant (91%, 95% and 86%, respectively), and that of cases with preserved E-cadherin expression/negative EMT status was much smaller (9%, 5% and 14%, respectively). In the group with metastatic gastric carcinoma in the lymph nodes, all studied metastases had high proliferative activity (proliferative index > 20%). The proliferative index of metastases with intestinal type GC is significantly higher compared to the metastases with diffuse type GC. We did not find a significant relationship between the values of the proliferative index in lymph node metastases on the one hand and the individual clinico-morphological indicators.

Conclusions: The proportion of tumors with reduced E-cadherin expression/positive EMP was predominant in both the general group and the groups with intestinal and diffuse type of GC, while the cases with preserved E-cadherin expression/negative EMP status were smaller. Proliferative indices in cases with advanced gastric carcinoma (pT3+T4) or lymphovascular invasion (LV+) were significantly higher compared to those with early tumor stage (pT1+T2) or without lymphovascular invasion (LV-).

Keywords: lymph node metastases, gastric carcinoma, E-cadherin, Ki67.

Introduction

According to Globocan data for 2020, gastric carcinoma is the fifth most commonly diagnosed malignant tumor worldwide and as a cause of death from malignant diseases in both sexes, it ranks in third place (1).

The incidence of gastric carcinoma varies worldwide with the areas with the highest incidence rates identified being East Asia (Korea), Eastern Europe, Central and Latin America and those with low incidence rates being North America, Northern Europe and Africa (2).

Gastric carcinoma is a most common disease in middle-aged and elderly people, more common in men than in women in a ratio of 1.6:1 (Globocan 2020).

Despite a steady decline in the incidence worldwide, the absolute number of newly diagnosed cases annually exceeds one million and is increasing mainly due to population aging (3).

Gastric carcinoma is a multifactorial disease in which both genetic and environmental factors play an important role in its etiopathogenesis.

Material and methods

Serial sections of 4µm thickness were prepared from selected paraffin blocks with primary gastric carcinoma and metastatic gastric carcinoma in the lymph nodes and mounted on adhesive slides. The sections were deparaffinized and rehydrated in alcohols of decreasing concentration and washing was performed with Bond™ Wash Solution according to the instructions for use. Before performing the immunohistochemical reaction, antigen retrieval was performed by incubation in Epitope Retrieval Solution 1, pH9 for E-cadherin and Ki 67.

The antibodies used against E-cadherin and Ki 67 were from Leica Biosystems Newcastle Ltd (Bond E-Cadherin, clone 36B5). Immunohistochemical expression of E-cadherin was recorded in the presence of staining in more than 10% of the tumor cells. The intensity of the immune reaction was defined as absent (0), weak (1+), moderate (2+), or strong (3+). Positive expression of Ki-67 was recorded in the presence of positive nuclear staining and a score of 0 - no positive tumor cells; score 1 - from 1-10% positive tumor cells; score 2 - 10-50% positive tumor cells and score 3 - 50-

100% positive tumor cells. The data from the studied clinical and morphological parameters and the results of the immunohistochemical studies of all studied patients with histologically proven gastric carcinoma were entered into an electronic database for subsequent statistical processing.

Results

We studied gender and age differences in patients with intestinal and diffuse type of gastric carcinoma. The characteristics of the studied patients with intestinal (n=97) and diffuse type of gastric carcinoma (n=61) according to age and gender, as well as by age under

and over 45 years showed that the incidence of gastric carcinoma in men in the total group of patients (n=158) was 2 times higher than that in women (68% vs. 32% or 2.1:1). In both groups of patients according to the type of gastric carcinoma, the proportion of men was higher than that of women, but without a statistically significant difference when comparing them.

The frequency of individual tumor stages (pT 1-4) in cases with intestinal and diffuse type gastric carcinoma, as well as in the general group, is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Histological diagnosis	pT stages				Total n (%)
	T1 n (%)	T2 n (%)	T3 n (%)	T4 n (%)	
Intestinal type	3 (5)	10 (18)	25 (45)	18 (32)	56 (100)
Diffuse type GC	2 (5)	11 (28)	10 (25)	17(42)	40 (100)
General group GC	5 (5)	21 (21)	35 (37)	35 (37)	96 (100)

The results show that in the group with intestinal type GC (n=56) the proportion of T3 tumors (45 %) was the largest, followed by that of T4 tumors (32%) and T2 tumors (18 %). In the group with diffuse type GC the proportion of T4 tumors (42%) is the largest, and the proportions of T2 and T3 tumors are similar (28% and 25%, respectively). In both groups there are single cases with early GC (pT1) – 3 (5%) and 2 (5%) cases for intestinal and diffuse type, respectively. The comparative analysis found that in both groups of gastric carcinoma the proportions of tumors with advanced tumor stage (pT3 and pT4) are significantly higher

(77% and 68% for intestinal and diffuse type, respectively) compared to those of tumors with early tumor stage (pT1 and pT2) – 23% and 32% for intestinal and diffuse type, respectively, but without a statistically significant difference.

We studied the nodal status (pN) of cases with intestinal and diffuse type of gastric carcinoma diagnosed on surgical resection material. The histopathological determination of the nodal status of the studied cases with intestinal and diffuse type of gastric carcinoma is shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Histological diagnosis	pN stages				Total n (%)
	N0 n (%)	N1 n (%)	N2 n (%)	N3 n (%)	
Intestinal type	24 (43)	15 (27)	12 (21)	5 (9)	56 (100)
Diffuse type GC	7 (18)	20 (50)	7 (18)	6 (15)	40 (100)
General group GC	31 (32)	35 (37)	19 (20)	11 (11)	96 (100)

The results show that the proportion of cases with histologically proven lymph node metastases (p N 1, p N 2 and p N 3 in total) is significantly higher in the group with diffuse type GC compared to intestinal type GC (83% vs. 57 % $\chi^2 = 6.034$, p=0.007). The histological analysis of the nodal status in the group with intestinal type of GC showed that the proportion of cases without lymph node metastases (p N 0) was the largest -43 %, and the proportions of cases with lymph node

metastases up to 5 (p N1) and over 5 (p N 2 and p N 3 total) were similar -27 % and 30%, respectively.

We studied the relationship between E-cadherin expression and individual clinico-morphological parameters.. The results of the performed comparative analyses of search for a relationship between E-cadherin expression and the studied clinico-morphological parameters in the group with gastric carcinoma lymph node metastases are given in Table 3.

Table. 3.

Relationship between immunohistochemical expression of E-cadherin and the studied clinico-morphological parameters in patients with metastatic gastric carcinoma in the lymph nodes.

Indicators	E-cadherin expression (color intensity)		p=
	Reduced (n=30)	Reserved (n=3)	
Gender			
Men (n=25, 100%)	24 (96%)	1 (4%)	NS p=0.072
Women (n=8, 100%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	
Age (years)			
Average age (S±X)	62.70±13.90	57.33±6.51	NS p=0.518
Degree of differentiation (grading)			
Low grade (n=11, 100%)	10 (91%)	1 (9%)	NS p=0.748
High-grade (n=22, 100%)	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	
pT stages			
Early - pT1+ pT2 (n=16, 100%)	14 (88%)	2 (12%)	NS p=0.509
Advanced - pT3+T4 (n=17, 100%)	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	
Nodal status (pN)			
pN1 (n=22, 100%)	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	NS p=0.4748
pN2 +pN3 (n=11, 100%)	10 (91%)	1 (9%)	
Lymphovascular invasion			
LV (+) (n=18, 100%)	17 (94%)	1 (6%)	NS p=0.439
LV (-) (n=15, 100%)	13 (87%)	2 (13%)	
Perineural invasion (PN)			
PN (+) (n=28, 100%)	25 (89%)	3 (11%)	NS p=0.443
PN (-) (n=5, 100%)	5 (100%)	0 (0%)	

Regarding the gender of the patients, we found that in women the proportion of metastases with reduced E-cadherin expression (75%) was lower than in men (96%), but without a statistically significant difference ($p=0.072$). The mean age of patients with reduced E-cadherin expression was older than that of patients with preserved E-cadherin expression, but the difference did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.518$). We did not find a significant relationship between E-cadherin expression on the one hand and on the other hand with the histological grading of the tumor, tumor

stage, nodal status, lymphovascular infiltration or perineural invasion. However, the proportion of cases with advanced tumor stage (pT3+pT4) and reduced E-cadherin expression was higher than that with early tumor stage (pT1 +pT2) - 94% versus 88%. We found the presence of reduced E-cadherin expression not only in cases with high-grade carcinomas, those with more than 5 lymph node metastases (pN2 +pN3), with lymphovascular infiltration or perineural invasion, but also in those with low-grade carcinomas, with <5 lymph node metastases (pN1) and without lymphovascular infiltration.

Photo 1 – E-cadherin, moderate intensity in diffuse gastric carcinoma, IHC, x100

We looked for correlation between the expression

of Ki-67 and individual clinico-morphological parameters in the group with metastatic gastric carcinoma in the lymph nodes. The immunohistochemical expression of Ki-67 was studied in 27 lymph node metastases from gastric carcinoma, of which 13 were of the intestinal type GC, and the remaining 14 cases – of the diffuse type GC. The presence of positive nuclear expression of Ki-67 was found in all studied metastases with a varying percentage of positive tumor cells (Fig. 47). In nearly 2/3 of the cases (n = 20, 74 %) nuclear expression of Ki-67 was reported in 50-100% of the tumor cells. In the remaining 7 cases (26%) Ki-67 expression was reported in 10-50% of the tumor cells. In both sub-

groups of metastases according to Lauren classification, the number of cases with Ki-67 expression in 50-100% of tumor cells was predominant - 10/13 (77%) for intestinal type GC and 10/14 cases (71%) for diffuse type GC. We did not find a significant difference between Ki-67 expression and the type of metastases according to the histological type of gastric carcinoma (p= 0.745).

The results of the comparative analyses performed to search for a relationship between the expression of Ki-67 and the studied clinico-morphological indicators in the group with metastatic gastric carcinoma in the lymph nodes are given in Table 4.

Table. 4

Relationship between Ki-67 expression and individual clinico-morphological indicators in the group with metastatic gastric carcinoma in the lymph nodes.

Indicators	Ki 67 expression		p=
	Expression in 10-50% (n=7)	Expression in 50-100% (n=20)	
Gender			
Men (n=20, 100%)	3 (15%)	17 (85%)	p=0.029
Women (n=7, 100%)	4 (57%)	3 (43%)	
Age (years)			
Average age (S±X)	64.43±13.45	61.65±13.49	NS p=0.643
Degree of differentiation (grading)			
Low grade (n=9, 100%)	3 (33%)	6 (67%)	NS p=0.535
High grade (n=18, 100%)	4 (22%)	14 (78%)	
pT stages			
Early - pT1+ pT2 (n=13, 100%)	2 (15%)	11 (85%)	NS p=0.228
Advanced - pT3+T4 (n=14, 100%)	5 (36%)	9 (64%)	
Nodal status (pN)			
pN1 (n=19, 100%)	6 (32%)	13 (68%)	NS p=0.446
pN2 +pN3 (n=8, 100%)	1 (13%)	7 (87%)	
Lymphovascular invasion			
LV (+) (n=14, 100%)	2 (14%)	12 (86%)	NS p=0.152
LV (-) (n=13, 100%)	5 (38%)	8 (62%)	
Perineural invasion (PN)			
PN (+) (n=22, 100%)	5 (23%)	17 (77%)	NS p=0.426
PN (-) (n=5, 100%)	2 (40%)	3 (60%)	

Picture 2. Ki-67. Strong nuclear expression in > 50% of tumor cells. Metastasis from gastric carcinoma in lymph node. IHC. x100

We did not find a significant relationship between the expression of Ki 67 on the one hand and on the other hand with the histological degree of tumor differentiation, tumor stage, nodal status, lymphovascular infiltration or perineural invasion. The presence of high proliferative activity (Ki 67 expression in 50-100% of tumor cells) was found not only in cases with high-grade carcinomas, those with more than 5 lymph node metastases (pN2 +pN3), with lymphovascular infiltration or perineural invasion, but also in those with low-grade carcinomas, with <5 lymph node metastases (pN1) and without lymphovascular infiltration.

Discussion

Gastric cancer is often diagnosed at an advanced stage (3). The TNM staging system is the most important guideline for choosing a therapeutic regimen and determining the prognosis of patients with gastric cancer (4). It is well known that lymph node metastases is the most important prognostic factor in patients with gastric carcinoma. However, even after radical resection of primary tumors and lymph nodes, about 20% of patients with gastric carcinoma die of recurrence (5). Several investigators have demonstrated the usefulness of immunohistochemical techniques for detecting metastases and micrometastases in lymph nodes of patients with gastric carcinoma (6). The incidence of nodal metastases is significantly higher in diffuse type than in intestinal type gastric carcinoma (7). Due to the complex mechanisms of initiation and progression of gastric cancer, its early detection and effective treatment is difficult. (8). Gastric cancer shows marked heterogeneity in terms of tumor growth, histogenesis and molecular pathogenesis. In the process of transcriptional regulation, several key transcription factors (including Snail, Twist and ZEB) play roles that suppress E-cadherin expression in gastric cancer. (9). Members of the protein family of Snail play a central role in regulating EMT during tumor progression by repressing E-cadherin transcription (10). Twist protein has recently been reported as an important regulator of carcinogenesis and tumor metastases in various solid tumors, including gastric cancer. Twist and Snail expression is associated with invasive carcinoma proliferation and is a poor prognostic factor.

It has been reported that decreased E-cadherin expression plays an important role in the development of lymph node metastases in patients with gastric cancer and the maintenance of an invasive phenotype (4,6). However, the relationship between E-cadherin expression in the primary tumor and that in lymph node metastases has not been extensively studied. The results suggest that loss of E-cadherin expression and positive EMP status may contribute to nodal metastases in patients with gastric cancer (7).

Reduced expression of E-cadherin has been found mainly in poorly differentiated tumors and in diffuse type of gastric cancer (10). Some authors reported that 63.6% of patients with signet ring cell carcinoma had confirmed E-cadherin mutations (Machado et al., 2001). Reduced expression of E-cadherin is an independent prognostic factor for gastric cancer. Chen et al (1 0) reported that loss of E-cadherin expression was significantly associated with tumor invasion.

Yonemura et al (1 1) also reported that reduced expression of E-cadherin showed a strong association with positive serosal spread and invasive phenotype. In the present study, the proportion of cases with advanced tumor stage (pT3+pT4) and reduced E-cadherin expression was higher than that with early tumor stage (pT1+pT2) - 94% vs. 88%.

Ki-67 is a well-known marker of proliferation and is widely used to assess the growth fraction of tumor cells. Ki-67 is a nuclear antigen that is present in proliferating cells and absent in quiescent (G0 phase) cells (1 2). Some studies have shown significantly higher Ki-67 in intestinal-type gastric cancer (1 3, 19). However, other studies have not demonstrated a correlation between neoplastic cell proliferation and histological type of tumors (15, 16). In our study, the proportions of cases with Ki67 expression in 10-50% of tumor cells were higher compared to those with Ki67 expression in 0-10% and 50-100% of tumor cells both in cases with advanced gastric carcinoma (pT3+T4), presence of lymph node metastases, lymphovascular infiltration, or perineural invasion, but also in those with early tumor stage (pT1 +T2), without lymph node metastases, without lymphovascular infiltration, or perineural invasion.

We did not find a significant association between Ki67 expression on the one hand and tumor stage, nodal status, lymphovascular or perineural invasion on the other. The difference between studies may be explained by the difference in assessment methods such as IHC staining. Parallel examination of Ki67 expression as a proliferative marker and E-cadherin as a structural adhesion protein can be used to define more aggressive phenotypes. in gastric cancer (17,18). Comparative analysis of these two markers may help in prognosis and therapy in case of tumor progression (20). We should not overlook the fact that the cases in our study were relatively small. More cases of gastric carcinoma are needed to draw conclusions about possible prognosis and therapy.

Conclusion

Reduced expression of E- Cadherin is associated with invasion and lymph node metastases in gastric cancer, which is a poor prognostic factor. We found high immunohistochemical expression of Ki 67 in all gastric carcinomas with lymph node metastases. In our study, there was no statistically significant difference between Ki67 expression and the degree of tumor differentiation, tumor stage, nodal status, lymphovascular infiltration, or perineural invasion.

Gratitude

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